

BASIC AND ADDITIONAL TERMS OF THE SURROGATE MOTHERHOOD CONTRACT

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7183865>

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Abstract: *This article describes the main and additional terms of the surrogate motherhood contract, the approaches to the rights and obligations of the parties to the contract. The article also covers the contractual legal basis of aspects of the surrogate motherhood contract related to the characteristics of the unnamed (atypical) contract.*

Key words: *Main terms and additional terms of the surrogate motherhood contract, Important, simple, random terms of the surrogate motherhood contract.*

In the countries of the world, the contract on surrogate motherhood is used as a new type of contract, but in the legislation of developed countries, the contract on surrogate motherhood cannot be called a novelty. The main reason for this is the improvement of legislation related to surrogacy contracts in a number of developed countries. In Asian countries, this type of contract has not been accepted in the legal documents for a long time under a certain name, but it exists in practice: "Also, during the study, it is known that the clinics operating in the city of Tashkent offer this service. For example, although the "Shahnozabanu Faiz" or "Doctor D" clinics do not directly provide surrogate motherhood services, they are able to provide advice to citizens in this field. When a citizen applies to these clinics and is informed by these clinics that they do not officially have a license to carry out this process, in practice, citizens are given the opportunity to submit all the necessary analyzes related to surrogacy and artificial insemination, and in the end, Kazakhstan This service is provided in clinics located in Shymkent, Estonia. In this case, first of all, the problem is caused by the imperfection of the existing legislation, and secondly, due to the high price of this service (5,000 US dollars on average), we see that a large amount of money is leaving our country to the neighboring Republic

of Kazakhstan.”¹ So, if we approach the issue with N.I. Askarov's opinion, the regulation of contractual relations related to surrogate motherhood service in our country is more relevant today than ever before. Based on this, although the provision of services based on the surrogacy program has been established in many countries, in practice, the program of surrogacy relations is not regulated by contractual and legal relations.

It should be noted separately that the surrogate motherhood contract is an independent type of contract made by potential parents to treat infertility and achieve family value, unlike other civil and family-legal contracts listed in the legislation of the countries of the world - the birth of a child work and the establishment of child-parent relations in the future. Due to the fact that the regulation of the contract by legal acts is limited only to showing the possibility of concluding it, the issue of the content of the contract remains at the discretion of the parties.

The content of the contract is a set of conditions agreed upon by its parties, the rights and obligations of the counterparties (lat. *contrahens* - contracting parties - the contracting party in civil legal relations) are strengthened, and constitute the content of the contractual obligation.² **It is reasonable to divide the terms of the contract reflecting surrogate motherhood into three groups: important, simple, and accidental.**

According to the establishment of civil-legal relations, if the parties have reached an agreement on all the important terms of the contract in the necessary form, the contract is considered concluded. Conditions on the subject of the contract, conditions specified as important or necessary for this type of contract in the law or other legal documents, as well as all relevant conditions at the request of one of the parties are important for reaching an agreement. Therefore, the important terms of the contract are the terms that define the essence of the contract and make it possible to distinguish it from other contracts.

On the other hand, simple conditions are conditions that exist in this type of contract, but the validity period of the contract does not depend on their consistency.

Incidental conditions are, as a rule, conditions that are not stipulated in this type of contract, but can be determined by the agreement of the

¹ Askarov N.I. Theoretical and practical problems of civil legal regulation of unnamed contracts. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation on legal sciences / T., 2020. Page 19

² Russian civil law: Textbook: In 2 vols. T. II: Law of Obligations / Resp. Ed. E.A. Sukhanov. - 4th ed., stereotype. M.: Statut, 2016. 147 page.

parties, and the validity of the contract does not depend on their agreement.

Researcher O.S. Ioffe, in his opinion on the subject of ordinary and accidental terms of the contract, believes that there is almost no need to include ordinary terms in the contract. The reason for this is that they are formulated in law or other regulatory documents, and since the counterparties agree to conclude this contract, they are recognized as having agreed to comply with the conditions applicable to the relevant type of contractual relations or to all contracts in general in accordance with the law. It should be noted that accidental conditions are not important for concluding a contract. If the usual terms are stipulated by law and therefore only come into force when the contract is concluded, the accidental terms can appear and have legal force only if they are included in the contract itself.³

Scholar S.P. Juravleva⁴, taking into account the legal regulation of surrogate motherhood, the following of the surrogate motherhood contract: Information about the persons participating in the surrogate motherhood program, the place of residence of the surrogate mother during childbirth, the rights and obligations of the parties, the consequences of the birth of a defective child, the surrogate Procedure and conditions for payment of material expenses for providing the mother, grounds and consequences of termination of the contract, liability of the parties for non-fulfillment of the terms of the contract, procedure and consequences of reimbursement of costs incurred by potential parents for the surrogacy program. If the surrogate mother is the parent of the child reserves the right to "refusal" the transfer of the child to potential parents, suggests considering other conditions determined by the agreement of the parties as important.

Researcher A.S. Kolomiets, who consistently analyzed surrogate motherhood relationships, provided the following information on the surrogate motherhood contract: the price of the contract, the medical institution or institutions where the procedures will be performed, the number and types of procedures and tests to be performed by the surrogate mother. According to Kolomiets⁵, the following are accidental

³ Ioffe O.S. Soviet civil law. M.: Yurid. lit., 1967. 387-388 pages

⁴ Juravleva S.P. Legal regulation of the contract on surrogate motherhood in the Russian Federation: author. Ph.D. legal Sciences. M., 2011.

⁵ Kolomiets A.S. Grounds for the onset of civil liability under a surrogate motherhood agreement // Nauka. Society. State. 2013. No. 4

conditions: the requirements that the surrogate mother must meet, the setting of various obligations for the surrogate mother (schedule, place of residence, food), the obligation of the surrogate mother to follow the reasonable instructions of the doctor, the father ordering the birth child - the time and place of transfer to the mother, the time and place when the surrogate mother signed the consent to the transfer to the name of the biological parents of the child, confidentiality and availability of information, the surrogate mother agreed to give birth in the case of multiple pregnancies notes that the number of children, the obligation of the genetic parents to accept the child, and the legal consequences in the case of the death or divorce of the clients are important conditions.

Another group of researchers calls the important condition of the surrogate motherhood contract only the condition on the subject of the contract.⁶ In our opinion, all the above terms are not essential terms of the surrogacy agreement. According to the above-mentioned legal grounds, if an agreement is reached between the parties on all important terms of the agreement in the form required in relevant cases, the agreement is concluded. From this we can conclude that the main terms of the contract are the terms that define such a contract and allow it to be clarified among many other contracts.

If the important terms are not agreed upon by the parties (if they are not included in the text of the contract), then such an agreement is considered not concluded, if the important terms of the agreement are agreed, then the agreement is considered concluded. It follows that essential terms are the minimum set of contractual terms that allow the parties to confirm that they have concluded a contract and are obligated to perform it.

In accordance with the civil legislation, the conditions on the subject of the contract are all the conditions specified by the law or other legal documents as important or necessary for this type of contract, and according to the statement of one of the parties, they are all the conditions necessary to reach an agreement.

In our opinion, the first important condition of the contract on surrogate motherhood is the condition on the subject of the contract. This condition allows you to determine the main purpose of the contract and what result the parties want to achieve.

⁶ Surrogate motherhood contract. Electron resource. URL: <https://www.e-romanova.com/surrogatnoe-materinstvo/#axzz55Oo0KORV> (дата обращения 11.12.2018)

In short, the surrogate motherhood contract means that the surrogate mother undertakes to give birth to a genetically alien child for herself in the interest of the potential parents, transfers the parental rights to the genetic parents, and provides the necessary medical treatment indicated by the medical organization. So, it is an agreement between the parties that creates the obligation to provide the full range of services.

The medical aspect of surrogate motherhood involves a series of steps, including the selection of the necessary genetic material from the potential parents and the cultivation of the embryo, which is then implanted into the surrogate mother. If the infertility of the potential parents was considered to be related to the inability to give birth to a healthy child. In the meantime, if normal conclusions are reached for the concept and program of surrogacy (if the genetic material itself is valid), then it will be possible for the parents to participate in the program of surrogacy on medical grounds.

However, in some cases, potential parents may need to use donor genetic material to implement a surrogacy program. Such a need arises when a person's genetic material is not suitable for creating an embryo or when one of the potential parents refuses to participate in the surrogacy relationship after signing the contract. Therefore, the donation procedure is a necessary factor for the use of genetic material in the surrogacy program.

Thus, the condition of using one's own or the donor's genetic material is the next important condition of the surrogacy contract.

The rights and obligations of the parties are important as a basic condition because they reflect the content of their legal relationship and ultimately derive from the law. Therefore, it is determined that their consistency or inconsistency in the text of the agreement can affect the fact of concluding a contract or not concluding a surrogate motherhood contract.

The terms of payment of fees arising from surrogacy, its free basis, and the procedure for reimbursement of expenses do not determine the essence of the surrogacy contract as the main conditions, because the surrogacy contract is equally covered and free of charge.

The consequences of the birth of an unhealthy child, the conditions of multiple pregnancy and its consequences do not affect the existence or absence of a surrogate relationship and their inconsistency does not affect the validity of the contract. At the same time, a child born from a surrogate mother should, in any case, be transferred to potential parents who should be registered as parents. In this case, it is not important whether the child

has one or more, whether they are healthy or not. Therefore, based on the consequences of the client's divorce, it cannot be considered as an essential or customary condition of the surrogacy contract, since both potential parents, regardless of whether there is a marriage between them, are the genetic parents in the surrogacy program and the contract.

Otherwise, if it is recognized that the rights and obligations of the parties to the contract depend on the fact of separation between the potential parents, the presence of multiple pregnancies, diseases of the newborn, and the like, it is legally unacceptable. There is a situation of legal uncertainty in the fate of the future child. Since the child was born in the interest of the potential parents and was born on their initiative, the newborn baby, regardless of gender, health and other factors, is recognized as a child of the potential parents with all the legal consequences of such a factor must be registered.

In addition, information about the identity of the parties to the surrogacy contract is of great importance in surrogacy relations. Because the law imposes certain requirements on the surrogate mother, potential parents and medical organization that must be followed in order to participate in the surrogate motherhood relationship. In other words, these requirements are the requirements that the subjects must fulfill in order for the parties to have the opportunity to conclude a surrogate motherhood contract.

If at least one of the parties to the surrogate motherhood contract does not meet all mandatory criteria, then the surrogacy contract is not concluded.

At the same time, the legal requirements for the subjects of the surrogate motherhood contract cannot be considered as important terms of the contract. However, if the potential parents want to impose additional requirements on the surrogate mother (for example: race, religious beliefs, genetic characteristics, the presence or absence of past diseases, the presence or absence of any habit etc.), in which such requirements can be recognized as additional requirements in the surrogacy contract as important conditions with the nature of the main condition. The practice of the same content is considered to be relevant to the requirements for the medical organization.

We can conclude from the above comments as follows. In accordance with the principle of freedom of contract, potential parents, as customers and initiators of legal relations on surrogate motherhood, have the right to submit additional criteria to the surrogate mother and the

medical organization in addition to the requirements established by law. It is important that the additional conditions cannot contradict the basic conditions.

Since the surrogate motherhood contract is the only legal mechanism designed to regulate legal relations on surrogate motherhood, additional requirements can be imposed on surrogacy subjects only by including relevant conditions in the text of the surrogate motherhood contract can be entered.

From the above analysis, it can be noted that if the potential parents add new requirements to the contract in the surrogate motherhood contract, then such conditions are considered important and such conditions can be considered as basic conditions.

In our opinion, the main conditions of the surrogate motherhood contract should be as follows:

- a condition set on the subject of the contract;
- the condition of using one's own or the donor's genetic material;
- the condition that there are additional requirements for the surrogate mother and the medical organization.

In turn, other conditions of the surrogate motherhood contract, for example, the rights of the parties, the procedure for mutual settlement, the obligations of the parties, the procedure and conditions for terminating contractual relations, the conditions for conducting additional medical studies, etc. it was considered appropriate to be accepted as conditions.

As a conclusion, based on the content of the surrogate motherhood contract, it should be noted that this contract is complex. The contract of surrogate motherhood includes a number of contractual functions. However, according to experts and scientists from Western Europe and the United States, the surrogate motherhood contract should be multilateral. Each of the parties to the contract is obliged to fulfill the respective obligations to each other based on the duties that they perform.

Due to the fact that the surrogate motherhood contract has its own characteristics, special requirements are imposed on the parties that aim to conclude this contract. The parties to the surrogate motherhood contract are the surrogate mother, the genetic father and the medical organization implementing the surrogacy program.

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